

Developing Postal Platforms

Working with the private sector

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decision/analysis partners LLC

The concept of platform

The International Postal Corporation (IPC) and the USPS' Office of Inspector General (OIG) have both recently shown interest in the concept of digital platforms and their applicability to the postal world. Professor Marshall Van Alstyne, Associate Professor of information economics at Boston University/MIT, provided both organizations with overviews of his research in this area.

Typical examples of digital platforms include desktop operating systems such as UNIX, Mac and Windows; PDAs such as Palm, Psion or Newton; game consoles; payment systems; and mobile devices such as iPhone, Android, Symbian or BlackBerry. The success of these platforms has relied on the presence of networks of users and providers, and common components that create sustainable eco-systems.

Fig. 1 on the next page shows the four key stakeholders of a platform and its supporting eco-system¹.

Users, the demand side. These are the target consumers of the platform solutions and services.

Solution developers, the supply side. They provide services that attract users to the platform.

Providers. The Microsoft Windows operating system was mainly provided to users by PC manufacturers when they acquired their computers, not direct by Microsoft. Providers are typically the contact

point for the developers and the users.

Sponsors. Sponsors are usually responsible for providing the overall organizing structure for a platform, its rules and governance. This may include the original design of the platform and control of its underlying technology and the overall intellectual property rights. A sponsor's objective is to make other participants see how they are better off by being part of the

¹Eisenmann, T, Parker, G. & Van Alstyne, M (2009) "Opening Platforms: How, When & Why" Ch 6 in Platforms, markets and innovation, A. Gawer (editor) Edward Elgar Publishing pp 131-162.

system rather than outside of it.

What renders a platform successful is the network effect. Users are attracted to the platform because of the innovative solutions it makes

Figure 1

available to them. Entrepreneurs and solution developers are attracted to the platform because of the potentially lucrative number of users looking for solutions and value. These desirable network effects do not happen by chance. They are the result of well engineered, well designed rules upon which these platforms are built, and which encourage solution developers to bring their innovative ideas and energy to a platform. These rules basically open the platform to outside private investors by sharing revenue and intellectual property, and by providing the right amount of central development and strategic guidance.

Research shows that the level of openness in governance rules plays an important role in the success of the platform. For instance, the MySpace social network was a closed platform where management required all development to be per-

formed within the company. Facebook, on the other hand, made the decision to open itself to outside applications and developers. A comparison between the two platforms shows that Facebook's number of users shot up considerably compared to MySpace once they decided to do this.

Private participation in postal solutions

Posts around the world are confronted with significant challenges caused by the decline in traditional mail volumes and competition from private operators. Posts need to develop strategies that create new sources of revenue, yet maintain the essential role of the post in society.

Of course posts already operate platforms, mainly physical distribution platforms, sometimes coupled with banking services. The challenge is to gain access to new platforms and to new sources of revenue. Several posts have indeed developed solutions. A good example is Swiss Post, as its CEO explains elsewhere in this issue of the Review. Such solutions are offered and managed by the post itself, and integrate with its distribution network and platform. Development of such solutions represents an important and positive step for posts, with the promise of new customers, and increased revenues from existing ones.

We believe, however, that

opening the postal infrastructure to privately sponsored and operated solutions would represent a more significant opportunity for posts, introducing the private sector to support a strategy that will be less risky, more innovative, and more successful.

Less risky. By opening up the postal platform to the private sector, posts will limit the amount of capital required to develop new solutions and new services that may sometimes bring disappointing results. This frees them to use their capital and resources for critical network infrastructure and platform investments.

More innovative. Private participation will bring more innovation and experimentation. Control of the platform by postal operators will ensure a public sector orientation, while opening it to the private sector will bring in innovation and drive. This will bring new thinking, new domain expertise (for instance, in depth knowledge of specific growing markets such as health care) and new experiences and qualifications.

More successful. This strategy, which reduces risk and increases innovation, will ultimately result in new value added services that complement the primary mission of the post, and, ideally, create network effects that bring more users and solution providers to the platform, thus increasing revenue.

Strategy for the introduction of new solutions

The success of the strategy to open the infrastructure to private solutions will depend, in part, on the types of services and solutions targeted by the post and its private partners. These solutions can range from services that exploit the official, universal nature of postal services, to those that leverage the commercial value of the information that can be collected about customers and users.

The official, universal nature of the postal service evokes services such as digital alternatives or complements to mail distribution. Others include electronic government services, and serving as an official interface between government and its citizens. Maintaining information privacy is critical to these types of solutions. At the other end of the spectrum are applications that try to leverage information about customers that would enable discovery of their preferences by analyzing the nature and content of mail and packages and thereby exploiting the so-called “Big Data”. It would be difficult for a postal operator to supply these two types of solutions at

the same time, claiming the utmost respect for privacy on the one hand, but monetizing it on the other.

Posts will need to take an aggressive approach to the adoption of new services in order to allow for the creation of network effects. This would include offering depth and breadth of services from the outset. For instance, if offering government support services, these should cover a wide range of popular needs spreading over many government agencies. If nascent or partial solutions already exist, they should be integrated into the new platform offering.

Another tactic is to work with high brand groups of users and solution developers to gain instant approval and traction, and, again, generate network effects. Co-opting high brands is also a way to prevent them from offering competitive services.

As Professor Van Alstyne points out, postal pricing relies almost always on the sender paying for shipping services. Under new solution

scenarios, however, revenues could be generated by third parties paying for information, or gathered from the receiver, especially if the services provide information or value the receivers are requesting and are willing to pay for.

Sample solutions

Below is a list of possible solutions that would open up the postal platform to private participation.

e-Gov/e-Gov Lite. Posts can leverage their privileged relationships with public agencies and with citizens to offer support with administrative formalities, helping citizens interface with government agencies, requesting, gathering and submitting records and forms to the right place on their behalf. This is sometimes referred to as e-Gov Lite because it does not require significant governmental process redesign. These services can be developed and managed by a private entity within the postal network, as is the case in Lebanon. The

solution leverages existing retail outlets, the postal network, and payment systems already in place. A software application can be used to automate and track requests, and break down each type of service to its workflow components to track progress, and make it easier to perform.

E-commerce. Some posts, such as Saudi Arabia, have developed e-commerce platforms, or, like Canada Post with BorderFree, integrated e-commerce more closely with their core business. In a private sector based approach, posts enable private companies to integrate more fully not only by exchanging information, but also through opening up the postal physical distribution network in such areas as integrated returns processing; determination of fully landed costs for dutiable shipments; track, trace and hold; online invoicing and payments; customer service; and business services such as storage, kitting, labeling and environmental disposal of spoiled items.

e-Mailbox/e-Lockbox. Posts have talked about providing digital services such as secure email for the purpose of converting physical mail to digital, integrating personalized multimedia in marketing campaigns, providing secure storage and archival of high value documents, and supporting e-government services. The Norwe-

gian and Finnish posts have developed such services, with varying degrees of customer acceptance. Canada Post has developed e-Post, in part, for users to receive bank statements, utility and credit card bills, and similar transactional correspondence. Our approach would solicit the private sector to come up with solutions already developed or partly developed, and jointly market them; and require the postal operator to provide infrastructural services such as user authentication, information privacy and data security.

Custom logistics. Posts can offer custom logistics services to complement their regular distribution mission. In our approach, operators open their distribution platforms with on and off ramps at various points in the postal distribution process. Private companies can process replacement parts through the postal infrastructure, or store kits within large postal plants, then assemble them, repack them or re-label them within the network. Solutions could leverage all elements of the distribution infrastructure, and address the specific needs of selected industrial sectors such as drug distribution, luxury items, perishable goods, etc.

AdMail/TransPromo. The post encourages private innovators to develop advertising solutions that leverage information about customers

and their preferences, focus on specific customer segments, merge transactional and advertising mail, or take advantage of available space. These solution providers could help design campaigns, mailing, mail production, and multichannel marketing for large as well as small businesses. Postal operator data could help these solution providers identify and target their customers, manage address lists, and create mailings, which, in turn, would generate traffic and additional revenues.

Next steps

Posts interested in pursuing a platform approach need to plan their strategy carefully. They must develop the vision, define the solution focus areas, and specify the business rules that will set the foundation for content, revenue and intellectual property sharing. Focus areas for solutions should be carefully evaluated, based on individual and business needs, the competitive situation, and the legislative environment. Posts should then engage in a campaign to identify potential private players, and put in place a replicable process to evaluate their proposed solutions. Finally, strict performance measures should be established to determine if and when failing solutions should be eliminated.

decision/analysis partners headed a workshop for OIG on digital platforms with Professor van Alstyne in November 2011, as part of a study on the digital divide.

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Delivery Management

AT A GLANCE:

D/AP OFFERS COMPREHENSIVE DELIVERY MANAGEMENT EXPERIENCE.

- APPLYING BEST PRACTICES IN DELIVERY MANAGEMENT.
- REVIEW AND REALIGN DELIVERY ROUTES BASED ON CHANGING VOLUMES
- IMPLEMENT A STRONG DELIVERY SUPERVISORY CULTURE TO IMPROVE PERFORMANCE
- PREPARE PERSONNEL TO TRANSITION TO DELIVERY POINT SEQUENCING
- ASSIST WITH ADDRESS MANAGEMENT TO PREPARE POSTS FOR AUTOMATION

decision/analysis partners offers practical **delivery management** advice and assistance to postal, mailing and shipping organizations, including private courier and delivery companies, smaller posts, and larger distribution organizations requiring sophisticated delivery planning and labor management.

Best Practices in Delivery Management

decision/analysis partners brings to every project the benefit of many years of experience, dozens of successful projects, and **best practices in delivery management**. Our teams help devise and implement delivery strategies that are consistent with corporate goals, labor constraints, human factors, and operational/performance requirements. Our approach is designed to reduce non-value-add activities, improve processes, operating discipline, reporting procedures, and increase customer satisfaction.

Route Planning & Adjustment

d/ap combines analytical techniques and strong subject matter expertise to design delivery routes that **reduce travel time & fuel usage**, maximize utilization of transport and casing equipment, and fully meet labor agreements. d/ap's delivery experts leverage state of the art route planning technology, as well as on-the ground observations and verifications, to readjust routes based on changing volumes, alignment with the delivery strategy and the corporate goals.

Delivery Supervision Development & Training

d/ap believes that efficient delivery requires a rigorous operating discipline, and competent supervision and oversight. d/ap helps companies develop a strong delivery supervisory culture through training. Working with senior delivery staff, we develop and conduct supervisor/manager assessment audits to identify skills deficiencies. We then develop leadership guides and customize training programs to improve supervisory leadership and performance.

Preparing for Delivery Point Sequencing

Posts that implement delivery point sequencing (DPS) must carefully prepare their delivery organizations for the expectations that DPS place on delivery. d/ap delivery experts ensure that the projected DPS savings are captured by:

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- Implementing address verification procedures to reduce sequencing error rates,
- Monitoring volumes by route/day/unit/type to devise sort schemes that are adapted to the mail densities per destination point,
- Evaluating potential equipment changes to improve utilization and flows of containers, cases, and delivery vehicles,
- Instituting supervisor-led on-going route adjustments processes,
- Integrating Operating Plans, Transportation Plans, and Delivery Plans to ensure proper synchronization of all business processes.

Address Management

Emerging economies and developing posts require address systems to take advantage of the digital world and start automating their operations. d/ap brings expertise and qualifications in building or improving address systems, validating actual street address data in both city and rural areas, in order to implement mail automation or delivery sequencing. We provide expert review of data base management and file structure to ensure seamless data flows for both internal and external customers.

About decision/analysis partners

decision/analysis partners is an independent technical and management advisory services firm offering operations management, business strategy, market analysis and technology consulting services in the postal, shipping and mailing industry.

Our approach uses sound and proven analytical methodologies to develop, evaluate, and help implement viable business solutions. Our team includes technical and management consultants, systems engineers, business architects, postal technologists, and postal operations managers. We have led major postal and logistics enterprise transformation initiatives.

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Labor Planning & Scheduling

AT A GLANCE:

- ENTERPRISE STRATEGY
- PRODUCT POSITIONING AND DEVELOPMENT
- MARKET ANALYSIS
- OPERATIONS AND NETWORK DISTRIBUTION STRATEGY
- OPERATIONS AND TRANSPORTATION MANAGEMENT
- POSTAL PLANT DESIGN
- ACQUISITION LOGISTICS
- STRATEGIC SOURCING
- SUPPLY CHAIN SECURITY

decision/analysis partners offers practical **labor planning and scheduling** assistance to help postal organizations optimize their labor costs while satisfying customer demand and service standards. A corporate wide framework is designed to drive the adoption of standardized methods and tools.

Labor Planning & Scheduling Assessment

Postal organizations struggle to understand how much labor is too much, and how little will affect service performance. d/ap develops an enterprise-wide assessment of labor planning and scheduling to evaluate how labor is managed on a yearly and daily basis, given labor agreements in effect. We identify the organization's current strategic plans, capacity plans, and employee scheduling processes, and determine how integrated they are into a unified framework of standardized business rules.

Integrated Planning & Scheduling

Working hand in hand with client postal organizations, decision/analysis partners establishes a work plan to develop methods and tools for labor planning and scheduling. Our approach is very targeted and focused – we build proofs of concepts, validate them throughout the postal organization, and standardize them as corporate-wide fully-documented methods and tools. We then proceed in an incremental manner, developing additional labor planning and scheduling capabilities, while keeping our eye on the overall framework.

Labor Reporting and Decision Support

To help Management reduce operating costs while meeting customer and service requirements, the labor planning and scheduling tools generate reports that focus on key performance indicators (e.g., target vs. actual labor by work center). More importantly, the tools are used as decision-support aids to evaluate the effects on costs and performance of various staffing scenarios and operations scheduling scenarios. These interactive decision-aids help take proactive labor scheduling decisions while guiding the end users in implementing sanctioned and preferred corporate practices.

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Modeling & Simulation for Decision-Support

AT A GLANCE:

D/AP'S MODELING EXPERTISE HELPS EXECUTIVES MITIGATE RISKS ASSOCIATED WITH COMPLEX BUSINESS DECISIONS. THIS INCLUDES:

- **RATIONALIZATION AND SIMPLIFICATION OF DISTRIBUTION NETWORK**
- **CAPITAL BUDGETING FOR ACQUISITION OF MAJOR TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS**
- **EVALUATION OF ALTERNATIVE TECHNOLOGY DESIGNS**
- **OPTIMAL STAFFING FOR MISSION CRITICAL PROCESSES**
- **IMPACTS OF VARIABLE LEVELS OF SERVICE ON LABOR, PROCESSING AND TRANSPORTATION COSTS**
- **OPERATING COSTS REDUCTION THROUGH DYNAMIC OPERATIONS SCHEDULING**

decision/analysis partners offers deep technical competence in **modeling and simulation** in support of complex postal, mailing and shipping projects, including **network and process modeling** for posts and larger distribution organizations involving complex material handling, business processes and/or distribution rules.

Modeling & Simulation to Mitigate Risk in Decision-Making

The proper evaluation of alternatives and their consequences is a necessary step in the mitigation of risks associated with any major operational decision. Modeling and simulation leverage robust analytical techniques that bring managers insights pertaining to each option. Modeling and simulation reduce the cost and time associated with the evaluation of alternatives and with overall decision making. decision/analysis partners brings strong expertise in the modeling of complex business situations in the postal, mailing and shipping domain under rapid turnaround.

Broad Range of Applications

The following are example of the application of modeling & simulation in decision/analysis partners projects:

1. A complex mail distribution network model to simulate processing network alternatives, and evaluate alternative distribution scenarios,
2. A capacity requirement analysis model to justify the procurement of mail processing equipment for mail and parcels processing centers,
3. An operational model to determine staffing requirements in a mail processing center during mission-critical mail dispatch operations,
4. A material handling model to evaluate design alternatives for tray handling systems in a new lettermail processing center,

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5. A model to dynamically schedule mail processing operations to optimize resources requirements.
6. An enterprise-wide model to evaluate levels of service impacts on operational costs – labor, processing, transportation,
7. A model to optimize bundling specifications for publications and flats to reduce processing and labor costs,
8. A model to evaluate the adequacy of a processing center parking lot prior to the processing center expansion.

decision/analysis partners has also supported executive decision-making by designing and developing simulation models for other industries, including minerals mining, airport baggage systems, batch and job shop manufacturing, and health care.

Building on the deep talent of decision/analysis partners, end users are provided with tools to support "what if" experimentation, and evaluate the risks associated with each outcome using dashboard summaries and, when needed, full 3D visualization.

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Postal Network Management

AT A GLANCE:

D/AP OFFERS A COMPLETE RANGE OF POSTAL, SHIPPING AND MAILING NETWORK MANAGEMENT ADVISORY SERVICES, INCLUDING:

- DISTRIBUTION STRATEGY TO EVALUATE NETWORK CONFIGURATIONS,
- NETWORK OPTIMIZATION TO BALANCE SORT & TRANSPORT
- SORT SCHEMES THAT MAXIMIZE ASSET UTILIZATION
- SURFACE TRANSPORTATION CENTERS TO OPTIMIZE SURFACE TRANSPORT
- TRANSPORTATION MODE ANALYSIS TO ENSURE LOWEST COST TRANSPORT

decision/analysis partners offers practical **network management** advice and assistance to postal organizations, ranging from smaller posts with one central sort center to large organizations requiring sophisticated automation and mechanization.

Distribution Strategy

decision/analysis partners (d/ap) helps postal operators devise an effective distribution strategy by optimizing the number of sorting centers, balancing time and transport versus economies of scale and scope. d/ap maintains a mid-size post comprehensive simulation model (ModelPost) and has developed complex models for large posts to evaluate the right distribution structure.

Network Optimization

Using mail volumes projections, trends in weights and shapes, demographic changes, costs of labor and transportation, we build and evaluate alternative network distribution scenarios to optimize current network configurations, minimize operating costs while respecting service standards. We review these scenarios with our client organizations and help them operationalize them.

Sorting and Delivery Sequencing

d/ap helps design sort schemes that leverage the entire distribution strategy while optimizing destination-point density, tray/container utilization, and transport utilization. Sort-strategies adapt to existing sorting equipment in order to reduce machine hours and associated labor hours, meet tie-out times, and maintain high asset utilization.

Surface Transportation Centers

Surface transport hub and spokes (HASPs) transshipment centers can play an important distribution role as part of an operator's network strategy. Our approach integrates HASPs as part of the postal operator or shipper's transport and network strategy to increase asset utilization and surface performance.

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Transportation Mode Analysis

d/ap takes a principled approach to the design of a postal operator network, and the determination of transportation modes (air – road – rail) to shape the network, locate plants, minimize costs, and ensure service performance. The processing and transportation components of the network are adjusted together to reflect relative changes in labor, fuel costs, or improvements in processing productivity to maintain the proper economic balance.

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Operations Management

AT A GLANCE:

D/AP OFFERS COMPREHENSIVE POSTAL, SHIPPING AND MAILING OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT ADVISORY SERVICES, INCLUDING:

- OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT STRATEGY TO ENFORCE DISCIPLINE AND ENABLE ADAPTABILITY.
- PLANT MANAGEMENT AUDITS TO IMPLEMENT SHORT TERM SERVICE IMPROVEMENTS AND LABOR-SAVING ACTIONS.
- NETWORK OPERATIONS CENTERS TO IMPROVE AGILITY AND REAL-TIME RESPONSE.
- OPTIMIZING 24-HOUR TIMELINES TO IMPROVE SERVICE AND REDUCE COSTS.

D/AP HAS DEVELOPED A NUMBER OF PRACTICAL TOOLS TO HELP POSTAL OPERATORS IMPROVE OPERATIONS:

- CAPACITY PLANNING
- ALTERNATIVE SORT STRATEGIES
- WORKFORCE PLANNING
- TIME-PHASED OPERATING SCHEDULES
- MAIL-FLOW MODELS

decision/analysis partners offers practical **operations management** advice and assistance to postal organizations, ranging from posts with few sort center to large organizations requiring sophisticated automation and mechanization.

Operations Management Strategy

Achieving operational excellence requires a strong operations management environment, disciplined, but also adaptable under changing conditions. decision/analysis partners has the expertise to implement such strong operational environments, starting with the creation of a strategy, and the development of documents such as **concept of operations** (ConOps), Required Operational Capability (ROC), and Projected Operational Environment (POE). These charter documents become the foundation for an integrated technology and operations planning approach.

Sortation Center & Mail Plant Management

d/ap process specialists and industrial engineers conduct **structured audits** of current plant operations, focusing on the root causes of service failures and costs buildups. We perform failure-modes and effects analysis (FMEA), and empirical analysis of key performance indicators (KPIs) to identify and recommend short-term and long-term improvements, balancing service performance, and labor and machine utilization.

Network Operations Centers

Network operations centers help postal organization become agile, balance asset utilization and manage network-wide emergencies. d/ap has designed and developed **network operations centers** (NOC) for large postal organizations from conceptualization to implementation. NOC support real-time decisions to manage distribution flows, modulate large customer inductions, and coordinate transportation operations.

24-hour Operating Timeline Analysis

We review and optimize existing sorting plant operating plans, testing alternative operating scenarios by varying the distribution rules, sort-scheme combinations, critical entry times and/or clear times, etc. Labor requirements

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are optimized for average and peak-volume days, and the plant's 24-hour timeline is optimized and re-integrated into the overall network operating plan.

Tools for Operations Management

decision/analysis partners has developed a number of operations management and decision-support tools:

- We have conducted **capacity planning** analyses to help a large operator plan its procurement budgets for letters and flats processing equipment.
- We have tested **alternative sort strategies** to produce optimal 24-hour operating plans under varying production scenarios (peak day, average day, day after holiday, etc.)
- We have developed **workforce planning** tools to align budgetary goals, set by headquarters, with operating requirements, defined by mail processing centers.
- We have designed and developed simulation-based models to produce **time-phased operating schedules** based on actual demand and labor availability, to optimize machine- and labor-usage.
- We have developed detailed **mail-flow models** to calculate staging and space requirements, by shift, for each work center within a plant.

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Plant & Work Center Design

decision/analysis partners helps organizations design and configure their letter-mail and parcel processing centers. We use best practices in **plant & work center design** by combining process management talent with industrial engineering and material handling expertise to optimize our clients' investments and operational costs.

AT A GLANCE:

D/AP OFFERS COMPREHENSIVE PLANT & WORK CENTER DESIGN ADVISORY SERVICES, INCLUDING:

- SORTING CENTER MAIL FLOW ANALYSIS
- DETAILED SORTING CENTER DESIGN.
- WORK CENTER DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION
- AUTOMATION & MATERIAL HANDLING EVALUATION
- TENDER DEVELOPMENT AND PROPOSAL EVALUATION
- INDEPENDENT TESTING AND EVALUATION OF SOFTWARE AND HARDWARE COMPONENTS AND SYSTEMS.

Sorting Center Mail Flow Analysis

d/ap uses a proven top-down planning approach to design letter-mail and parcel sorting centers that meet distribution requirements. Starting with a block layout analysis, we provide **design alternatives** and evaluate their dimension and cost implications on the new or remodeled center, taking into account volume projections, product mix, containerization alternatives, network distribution alternatives, and inbound/outbound transportation options.

Detailed Sorting Center Design

We refine the plant design by developing **detailed layouts** in close collaboration with our clients. Analyses include operational and material staging/handling space requirements, freight yards and loading docks analyses, architectural/structural requirements, mechanical/electrical requirements, and safety/environmental analyses. CAD renderings support the design selection.

Work Center Design & Optimization

Detailed work center designs generate **complete configurations of each work center** based on staging and flow requirements of trays/tubs and containers throughout the 24-hour cycle. We also evaluate freight yards and loading docks, as well as sorting center employee parking lot to determine the availability of spaces based on projected shift activity. Each work center design is documented in a report that describes mail flows, equipment/supplies requirements, space allocation and labor requirements.

Tender Development

d/ap assists its clients with the development of tenders for the acquisition of automation and material handling systems, software, or integration services. We develop functional, technical, maintenance, and performance requirements.

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We also develop independent cost estimates to facilitate the evaluation of tender cost proposals, perform vendor research, and develop tender strategies.

Automation & Material Handling Tender Evaluation

decision/analysis partners provides clients with technical **evaluations of tenders for automated and mechanized equipment, complex systems, and material handling installations**. We have specific experience with mail and parcel sorting equipment, storage systems, and other material handling systems. We follow a principled evaluation process which includes performance attributes, maintenance, installation, and various risk factors. Analytical techniques are used, if appropriate, and scores are presented to clients in the form of dashboards.

Independent Testing & Verification

d/ap has significant experience in developing and performing first-article test plans to verify that information systems and/or automation components satisfy tender technical specifications and requirements. We create test data or arrange for test material and schedule tests to minimize operational impact. We have performed tests in support of legal proceedings and comply to the highest standards of engineering and testing compliance.

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AT A GLANCE:

D/AP DEVELOPED A STATE-OF-THE-ART SIMULATION MODEL OF THE USPS OFFICE OF INSPECTOR GENERAL TO EVALUATE FACILITY CONSOLIDATION SCENARIOS.

THE ANALYSIS SHOWS THAT SIGNIFICANT CONSOLIDATION CAN BE ACHIEVED THAT WOULD PROVIDE SIGNIFICANT SAVINGS IN PROCESSING COSTS UNDER CERTAIN DISTRIBUTION CONCEPTS.

Simulation & Optimization of the United States Postal Network Infrastructure

SITUATION

The Postal Service processing and transportation (P&T) network infrastructure is at a crossroads, following decades of mail volume growth and breakthrough improvements in processing technology. With mail volumes predicted to drop over the next decades and mail patterns continuing to evolve, the USPS Office of Inspector General tasked decision/analysis partners (d/ap) with conducting a stakeholder survey and with developing an analytical model designed to evaluate first order P&T infrastructure scenarios using forecasted mail volumes.

APPROACH

d/ap conducted key interviews in the mailing industry, and developed a complex simulation model using Symphony REPAST, an open source application. The model follows these steps:

- A pre-processor sets a number of plants and hubs across the U.S. as part of scenarios.
- For each scenario, the model routes forecasted mail through facilities to destination while evaluating a number of distribution concepts (mesh, hub-and-spoke).
- Labor costs are determined as a function of the volume of mail and labor productivity in each facility, and added to transport costs.

RESULTS

The analysis conducted with the simulation model shows that the number of Postal Service letter and flat processing plants could be substantially consolidated to attain significant lower processing costs with minimal impact on service performance. Compared to today's 269 plants and 21 hubs, a scenario with 82 plants and 11 hubs shows minimum cost with some service degradation. A scenario with 172 plants and 18 hubs shows almost no service

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degradation. According to stakeholders, an opportunity exists through network consolidation to better align services offered with network capabilities to ensure that each service's speed and reliability are achieved.

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AT A GLANCE:

D/AP PROVIDED A COMPLETE REDESIGN OF THE MONTREAL LETTER PROCESSING CENTER AS PART OF CANADA POST'S MAJOR MODERNIZATIONS EFFORT.

CANADA POST TOOK OWNERSHIP OF THE CAPACITY MODEL DEVELOPED BY D/AP AS PART OF THE PROJECT.

Redesigning the Montreal Letter Processing Center

SITUATION

Canada Post Corporation (CPC) is undergoing a major modernization effort to equip itself with new mail sequencing equipment. The deployment of the new equipment requires a complete redesign of major processing centers with minimal building alterations and in a way that minimizes impacts on operations during the transition period.

CPC retained the services of decision/analysis partners (d/ap) to help design a plant layout that would accommodate all operating equipment, reduce non-value added mail movements, and minimize labor costs.

APPROACH

decision/analysis partners developed a comprehensive approach consisting of the following major steps:

- Developed block layout diagrams to identify key work centers and dimension them based on projected workload
- Built a detailed simulation model of the operations to estimate capacity requirements (number and type of processing equipment, and labor requirements)
- Developed detailed work center designs to estimate spatial requirements at work centers to accommodate for staging areas
- Developed multiple layout scenarios to present alternative options.
- Evaluated each option in terms of impact on operation during transition, adherence to safety standards, material flows between work-centers, expansion and/or building renovation requirements, and related costs.

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RESULTS

CPC adopted one of the layouts proposed, and has taken ownership of the capacity model built by d/ap to evaluate impacts of varying operational alternatives. The model is now being used by CPC as a planning tool to estimate labor requirements.

Montreal Scenario 2B V7
(05312009)

CPC
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